

Analysis of Daily Physical Activity by Garmin Smartwatches: A 7-Month Experiment

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Abstract—It is well-known, especially nowadays, how a regular amount of daily physical activity allows people to stay healthy, to reduce their risk of chronic diseases, and to improve their quality of life. To this end, technological solutions—in particular, wearable devices like smartwatches—can be considered as effective tools to enable self-monitoring of users, who can gain awareness of their health status and can possibly share information with medical personnel in the case of need. In this paper, an Internet of Things (IoT) architecture for long-time monitoring and daily physical activity quantification of healthy adults is presented. The proposed system exploits the availability of Garmin smartwatches worn by adult volunteers to collect multiple activity indicators, which are then properly processed in order to quantify the daily physical activity of each monitored subject. This is expedient to experimentally evaluate an innovative performance index, referred to as Physical Activity Index (PAI).

Index Terms—Internet of Things, IoT, Daily Physical Activity, Long-term Health Monitoring, Wearables, Physical Activity Index, PAI

I. INTRODUCTION

Among wearable technologies, smartwatches and wristbands represent the most popular devices worn every day by people all around the world: according to [1], in 2023 they generated an estimated global revenue of 24.62 and 7.62 billion USD, respectively. In particular, smartwatches own their popularity to their capacity to record and provide a number of indicators related to the consumers' health, including (i) physiological parameters, such as Heart Rate (HR) and Respiratory Rate (RR), (ii) sleep metrics, such as the quality and phases of sleep, and (iii) motion data, such as step count and physical activity information. In fact, the daily and continuous use of wearable sensors (i.e., smartwatches) provides the consumers with the ability to monitor their personal health status in real-time not only promoting self-care

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awareness, but also encouraging the adoption of such devices in clinical settings.

Moreover, several studies highlight the potential of employing smartwatches in the healthcare sector. As an example, the authors in [2] show how the use of commercial smartwatches might have a positive impact on modifying lifestyle behaviors. This is obtained by comparing health outcomes of two groups of participants who were asked to wear two different types of smartwatches, with and without blood pressure monitoring, respectively, for a 12-month period. The study reveals that participants wearing the smartwatch equipped with blood pressure monitoring—and motivated to be more physically active—show better values of some outcomes, such as HR at rest, body fat, Body Mass Index (BMI), and blood pressure. Other studies demonstrate how wearable devices may help reducing sedentary behaviors in favor of more active lifestyles. For instance, in [3] a mobile phone-based system is developed to support the self-management of hypertensive patients who discovered the importance of physical activity in reducing hypertension. In [4], the use of wearable activity trackers is demonstrated to increase physical activity in older adults with high risk of cardiovascular disease.

With regard to the parameters of interest related to physical activity, these might also include: step count, covered distance, and Energy Expenditure (EE). In [5], the validity of eleven wearable devices in measuring these three parameters is investigated in different walking and running conditions. In particular, Garmin smartwatches are demonstrated to be among the most accurate and reliable devices in measuring the step count, whereas all the considered devices exhibit a lower accuracy in measuring the covered distance and EE. The accuracy level of Garmin smartwatches is also investigated in [6] on a cohort of elderly people, obtaining an optimal agreement between step count measurements obtained by Garmin smartwatches and a handy-tally counter used as gold standard. This supports the reliability of Garmin smartwatches in quantifying the physical activity of elderly people in a real-life setting. Finally, other studies validating the use of Garmin smartwatches to monitor daily physical activity include the research activities described in [7]–[9], where the accuracy of HR, EE [7], and step count [8], [9] measurements is assessed, respectively.

Fig. 1: Block diagram of the steps of the data collection strategy. The involved entities are highlighted.

Given the importance of regular physical activity in preventing and reducing risks of chronic diseases, as suggested in [10], and given the effectiveness of smartwatch devices in monitoring health indicators, as demonstrated in the literature, this work aims at analyzing and quantifying the daily physical activity of adult subjects by Garmin smartwatches. In detail, exploiting an Internet of Things (IoT) network, various health parameters are considered to provide a novel and concise activity index, referred to as Physical Activity Index (PAI), derived on the basis of official regulatory guidelines and state-of-the-art references. The PAI is calculated as a weighted sum of specifically selected indicators, related to physical activity—expressed as percentages with respect to reference thresholds further motivated in Subsection II-B. The participants were monitored over a 7-month period during their daily activities. To this end, the experimental evaluation of the information collected via Garmin smartwatches confirms the quality of these monitoring devices in returning useful and insightful data for human characterization.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the method defined for sensing daily physical activities is detailed. The procedure used to retrieve data of interest from Garmin smartwatches is presented in Subsection II-A, while data processing tasks are detailed in Subsection II-B. Preliminary experimental results are discussed in Section III. Finally, in Section IV we draw our conclusions and pave the way to possible future research directions.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

In this study, the daily physical activity of 6 healthy adults, aged between 25 and 50, is analyzed over a period spanning 7 months. The participant pool is composed by 3 female and 3 male volunteers, all working as researchers and professors at the University of Parma, which can be considered as a relatively sedentary work. However, all the monitored subjects perform some physical activity at amateur levels (e.g., yoga, strength training, running, etc.). In detail, all the participants

were made aware of the aim of the proposed study and of the modalities of data collection through a written informed consent form, which was required to be signed before the effective data collection campaign started. Moreover, the participants gave their consent to the use of their personal data (name, surname, age, and gender), as explicitly declared in the signed informed consent form. In this study, motion data and training information are also collected as *raw* information sampled by the employed wearable devices. In particular, the participants were provided with Garmin smartwatches—namely, Garmin Fēnix 7s, Garmin Forerunner 255, Garmin Instinct 2 Solar—which they were asked to wear for the entire duration of the study (day and night). The participants were allowed to remove their smartwatches only for charging reasons and were asked to record all their training sessions.

A. Data Retrieval

In order to retrieve daily health data of interest of all the involved participants, we exploited the HTTPS APIs provided by Garmin through its Garmin Connect Developer Program [18]. In particular, the data related to participant were “pushed” by the Garmin HTTPS APIs to a dedicated Web platform, specifically created for the experimentation. For the purpose of accessing the users’ data, the following steps, summarized in Fig. 1, were followed.

- Each participant had to associate his/her Garmin smartwatch with a compatible smartphone by downloading the Garmin Connect App from the proper official App store and create a personal Garmin account. Each Garmin smartwatch automatically synchronizes with the associated smartphones exploiting the Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) connection available on the smartphone itself.
- Each participant creates a personal account on the developed Web platform and, once signed in, he/she had to grant our platform the access (with the right privileges) to the Garmin platform. This interaction is based on the OAuth 2.0 mechanism, with the Garmin Connect portal

TABLE I: Reference threshold values chosen for the considered activity parameters.

Parameter (i)	Threshold Value	Ref.
Step count per day (1)	10000	[11], [12]
Climbed floors per day (2)	8	[13]
Intensity minutes per week (3)	300 moderate + 150 vigorous	[14], [15]
PAL per day (4)	1.85	[16]
Active minutes per day (5)	120	[17]

representing the user data’s maintainer (and retention) infrastructure. In particular, OAuth 2.0 is used as a secure way for users to share their personal Garmin data without disclosing their private Garmin account credentials. In fact, the specifically developed Web platform (acting as the *client*) accesses the protected resources owned by the Garmin Connect Portal (acting as the *server*) by means of *access tokens* issued by the server after proper authentication and authorization of the client.

Finally, once the aforementioned steps are completed, the designed Web platform can synchronize with the Garmin Connect system and receive (in an asynchronous way, i.e., every time the user synchronizes the Garmin through his/her smartphone) the data of each participant who granted access to them—in particular, exploiting the Health APIs [19]. This avoids the need to “poll” the Garmin systems, saving energy and processing resources.

B. Data Processing

In order to analyze the daily physical activity of the participants, a PAI is derived on the basis of official regulatory guidelines and state-of-the-art literature references, as mentioned in Section I. In particular, the following 5 parameters are considered to quantify the daily activity of a subject: *step count*, *climbed floors*, *intensity minutes*, *active minutes*, and *Physical Activity Level (PAL)*.

- Step count and climbed floors have clear meanings.
- Intensity minutes are earned and cumulated (i) during training sessions and (ii) when standard activities are automatically detected (e.g., walking). Then, this information is classified into *moderate* and *vigorous* according to the intensity of the monitored activity, which is in turn measured by comparing HR data of the subject during the activity with his/her average resting HR.
- Active minutes refer to the portion of monitoring period in which the subject is considered active (i.e., not sitting or laying) according to heuristics internal to each device, as detailed in the Health APIs’ documentation.
- The PAL is defined as the ratio between the total EE and the basal metabolic rate estimated over a 24-hour period [16].

On the practical side, as a first step to calculate the PAI, a partial percentage of activity is computed for each considered parameter. This percentage is computed by comparing the parameter value with a reference threshold corresponding to the minimum value of the parameter needed to be considered

active. All the thresholds are set by taking into account specific recommendations by international organizations, such as World Health Organization (WHO) [20] and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) [21], and literature references. For clarity and completeness, the list of thresholds chosen for each parameter is detailed in Table I, where reference sources are also indicated.

With regard to Table I, each threshold value refers to daily amounts, except for intensity minutes, which are considered over an entire week, as suggested by the official regulations [14], [15]. In particular, it has been found that adults need 150 or 75 min of moderate- or vigorous-intensity activity per week, respectively, or a combination of both, in order to stay healthy. However, further benefits can be obtained with 300 and 150 minutes of moderate- or vigorous-intensity activity per week, respectively. This motivates the choice of the intensity minutes’ threshold in Table I. The threshold for climbed floors has been, instead, arbitrarily set to 8, considering a value larger than 5, as suggested in [13], and smaller than 10, which is set by default in Garmin smartwatches. The five chosen parameters are all proved to be valid indicators of the amount of physical activity, as demonstrated by the corresponding literature works mentioned in Table I. This further motivates the decision to derive a comprehensive index taking into account all of them.

Finally, PAI can be derived as the following weighed sum of the partial percentages of activity obtained for each considered parameter:

$$\text{PAI} = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i p_i \quad (1)$$

where, as shown in Fig. 2: $N = 5$, since 5 parameters are considered in this study; $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ corresponds to the i -th parameter as indicated in Table I; $w_i = 1/N = 0.2$ corresponds to the weight associated to the parameter i ; p_i corresponds to the partial percentage of the i -th activity. PAI can be interpreted as the total daily percentage of activity of a subject.

III. RESULTS

The participants were monitored for 7 months, from Monday June 3, 2024, to Sunday, January 5, 2025, for a total of 31 weeks, thus confirming and demonstrating the feasibility of the monitoring system outlined in Section II. More in detail, the PAI has been computed on a daily basis for each participant and, then, the average value per week has been

Fig. 2: Generic representation of the $N = 5$ components considered in the current version of the PAI.

derived, as shown in Fig. 3. For each day, the intensity minutes are obtained through a moving average with a sliding window covering the previous 7 days, since the official regulations consider weekly amounts of physical activity (instead of daily), as discussed in Subsection II-B. According to this strategy, the first monitoring week (Monday June 3, 2024–Sunday June 9, 2024) is excluded from the analysis and 30 weeks out of 31 are shown in Fig. 3.

Focusing on the results in Fig. 3, it can be immediately noticed that the average PAL per week can be considered constant for each analyzed subject. This parameter, indeed, is different for each subject since it depends on the individual basal metabolic rate, which is unique and is influenced by factors such as age, sex, weight, height, and BMI. For this reason, even if the variations of the total EE from day to day are relatively small (e.g., 1800–2200 kcal, assuming a basal metabolic rate of 1600 kcal), the average value of the PAL over a week remains more or less constant, considering that a subject is likely to alternate training days (more active) to rest days (less active) within the week.

Another observation, which can be inferred by looking at the results in Fig. 3, is that intensity minutes and active minutes do not seem to be correlated, i.e., active minutes do not include intensity minutes. Indeed, when the active minutes value is high (for example, in week 16 for subject n.2), the intensity minutes value is not necessarily high, whereas other values, such as climbed floors and step count, might be. However, active minutes and step count seem to have a quite high correlation, as further investigated in Fig. 4, where a linear regression model is overimposed to relevant data for each monitored subject.

Furthermore, for completeness, the correlation coefficient between active minutes and step count is detailed in Table II for each monitored subject. Thus, it can be highlighted that the highest correlation coefficient is obtained for subject n.1,

TABLE II: Correlation coefficient between active minutes and step count for each subject involved in the experimental study.

Subject	Correlation coefficient
n.1	0.9607
n.2	0.8924
n.3	0.9082
n.4	0.8725
n.5	0.8492
n.6	0.8972

who is also the most active participant—as confirmed by the PAI values shown in Fig. 3. Nevertheless, a good correlation can be observed for all subjects, since all the obtained correlation coefficients are higher than 0.89. No other significant correlation among the considered parameters emerges.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the feasibility of a smartwatch-based system to monitor the daily physical activity of healthy subjects in the long term has been demonstrated through the definition of an innovative metric, denoted as PAI, to quantify this activity. The PAI is defined and calculated (on a daily basis) for each monitored subject, relying on well-established threshold values of all health parameters involved in the PAI itself. Then, it is shown that the average PAI per week is obtained, with correlations between the considered activity parameters being investigated.

With regard to future research directions, the effectiveness of the proposed monitoring system will be assessed by comparing the experimental results with a *gold standard* used as a reference, and considering a more extended and diverse participant cohorts (in term of age, health status, physical activity and work) to generalize and sustain findings. After

Fig. 3: Average value per week of the considered PAI metric computed for the 6 subjects—(a) subject n.1 to (f) subject n.6—monitored over a 30-week period.

a proper validation, the system could be adopted in medical settings, representing a “secondary assistance solution” to physicians interested in continuously monitoring the health status of their patients. The system would also be optimized by integrating a way to provide a personalized feedback to the users on the basis of their computed daily PAI. Another relevant future activity, include the application of statistical or Machine Learning (ML) techniques to obtain deeper insights on participant activities, such as anomaly detection, pattern/activity recognition, or sport performance assessment. Finally, the proposed index will also be further improved defining different strategies to assign different weights to the considered component health parameters, taking into account factors such as age, sex, or personal goals.

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